

Studies on the Sorption and Desorption of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3$ on Bentonite

J. L. Das Kanungo, S. K. Chakravarti and S. K. Mukherjee

Adsorption and desorption studies of hexamine cobaltic chloride on and from a bentonite clay show that adsorption is according to Langmuir's equation and the desorbing cations conform to the lyotrope effect. Quaternary cations such as cetyl trimethyl ammonium (CTA^+) and cetyl pyridinium (CP^+) ions desorb more strongly than the inorganic ions; CP^+ having a smaller c.m.c. than CTA^+ is a more efficient desorbing ion. At higher concentration, $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$, has higher desorbing power than $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^+$ which may be due to the comparatively low activity of the latter than the former; at low concentrations, however, as expected, the reverse effect is observed. The experimental data strongly suggest that in the process of desorption of trivalent complex cation from the clay surface the Debye-Hückel parameter a° rather than the hydrated ionic radius may be found to correlate with the relative affinities of univalent and bivalent cations for montmorillonite surface.

Systematic studies of cation exchange in pure clay minerals carried out by different workers reveal that certain specificities in the exchange behaviour may be traced to the lattice configurations of the clay minerals¹⁻⁴. Specificities such as cation-effect with respect to exchange capacity of clay minerals have also been carried out by Mukherjee.⁵ Most of the earlier investigations on exchange equilibria, selectivity etc. were primarily based on the results of interaction of clays with simple inorganic^{6,7} and organic cations^{8,9} but very little study on the adsorption and desorption of inorganic trivalent complex cations^{10,11} has been reported so far; the physico-chemical aspects of many of these reactions being still unknown in their fundamental details. It is in this context that an attempt has been made in the present investigation to study the sorption and desorption characteristics of hexamine cobaltic chloride on bentonite.

EXPERIMENTAL

A bentonite fraction having particle size $<2.0\mu$ was isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation of Saurashtra bentonite (supplied by Calcutta Mineral Supply Co. Ltd.). It was converted into the H-form by resin (Dowex 50W-X8 and Dowex 2-X8) treatment and its b.e.c. was found to be equal to 110 m.e./100 gm. by

1. J. B. Page, and L. D. Bayer, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1939, **4**, 150.
2. A. L. S. Bar, and H. J. E. Tendeloo, *Koll. Beih.*, 1936, **14**, 97.
3. H. B. Hendricks, and L. T. Alexander, *Proc. Soil. Sci. Soc., Amer.*, 1940, **5**, 95.
4. P. Schachtschabel, *Koll. Beih.*, 1940, **51**, 199.
5. S. K. Mukherjee, Bulletin No. 6, *Indian Soc., Soil Sci.*, 1951, 89-95.
6. C. E. Marshall, 'The colloid chemistry of silicate Minerals', Academic Press, Inc., N. Y. 1949.
7. Adinath Basu, *J. Indian Soc. Soil. Sci.*, 1958, **6**, No. 2, 71-76.
8. S. K. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1959, **7**, 27-35.
9. D. K. De, S. K. Chakravarti and S. K. Mukherjee, *Science & Culture*, 1966, **32**, 182-183.
10. I. Martin, and R. Glaeser, *Bull. Groupe Franc. Argiles*, 1960, **12**, No. 7, 83-8.
11. J. L. Das Kanungo, S. K. Chakravarti and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian. Chem. Soc.* 1967, **44**, No.4, 339-344.

BaCl₂—Ba(OH)₂ method. The adsorption of hexammine cobaltic chloride Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ was studied first. A definite amount of bentonite suspension was taken in a number of pyrex bottles and different amounts of Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ were added. The bottles were then shaken for two hours and kept overnight to attain equilibrium. These were then centrifuged (2000 r.p.m.) for 15 mins. or so and Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ content was estimated from absorbance measurements with the supernatant liquids using the Zeiss photoelectric grating colorimeter 'Spekol'. The pH of salt plus clay mixture before and after adsorption varied between 3.70 and 3.35. The maximum adsorption of Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ corresponds to 100 m.e./100 gm. which is somewhat less than the b.e.c. The H-bentonite was then mixed with cobaltammine chloride in concentrations approximately 300 me./100 gm., i.e., three times the b.e.c. After 24 hrs. the excess salt was washed out with distilled water till the leachate gave zero optical density. The resulting clay was then resuspended in water. For studying desorption 10 ml portions of the above suspension (1.72%) were taken in a number of pyrex bottles and varying amounts of chlorides of different metals were added. The upper limit of the final concentration of the electrolytes was kept about 0.36M. These were then shaken for 2 hrs and allowed to equilibrate overnight, centrifuged for 15 mins. or so and the Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ content was estimated colorimetrically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adsorption isotherm of Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ on H-bentonite is shown in Fig. 1. The adsorption data are seen to fit well into the Langmuir adsorption equation (Fig. 1). It is evident from the graph that no multilayer formation takes place in the range of concentration of Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ studied. The desorption isotherms are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 and the calculated Distribution and Selectivity Coefficients corresponding to a definite concentration of the desorbing electrolyte are given in Table I. It is observed that compared to the quaternary ions the inorganic cations desorb Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ to a much smaller extent. Both kinds of ions, however, desorb in increasing amounts with the concentration.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherm of Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃ on H-bentonite.

It will be noticed that the value of the Selectivity Coefficients follow the lyotrope series being in the order: Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺ < NH₄⁺ < Rb⁺ < Cs⁺ for the monovalent, and Mg²⁺ < Ca²⁺ < Ba²⁺ for the bivalent cations. For the organic ions used the Selectivity Coefficients are in the order: (CH₃)₄N⁺ < (C₂H₅)₄N⁺ < CTA⁺ < CP⁺ in the low concentration

FIG. 2

Fig 2. Desorption of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{+3}$ from clay- $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6$ complex with electrolytes.

FIG. 3

Fig 3, Desorption of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{+3}$ from clay- $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6$ complex with electrolytes,

range. The order is reversed at high concentration in the case of the tetraalkylammonium ions (cf. Fig. 2). The reversal may be due to the comparatively low activity¹² of the former at higher concentrations. The desorption behaviour of the large organic cations studied has been found to be of considerable interest. It is noted that the efficiency of large organic cations in desorbing $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{+3}$ from its bentonite complex is much more than that of the inorganic cations. The peculiar behaviour of these reagents may be due to their strong adsorbability⁹, geometrical relationship to the surface, surface-active properties¹³ and their stronger affinity for the altered clay surface¹³. The desorption studies with the quaternary electrolytes have been carried out at concentrations exceeding their critical micelle concentrations, so that the multiple charged micelles are the actual desorbing species. CP^+ is found to be more efficient than CTA^+ because of its lower c.m.c. ($8.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$) than the latter (c.m.c. = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$).

TABLE I

Electrolyte used 1:1 electrolytes	Concentration of the electrolyte	Distribution coefficient	Selectivity coefficient
LiCl	0.16 M	0.81	0.11
NaCl	"	1.0	0.14
KCl	"	2.37	0.49
NH_4Cl	"	2.6	0.58
RbCl	"	4.8	1.63
LiCl	0.08 M	0.7	0.067
NaCl	"	1.0	0.115
KCl	"	2.5	0.38
NH_4Cl	"	2.7	0.43
RbCl	"	6.5	1.43
CsCl	"	10.5	4.1
2:1 electrolytes :			
MgCl_2	0.16 M	1.4	0.26
CaCl_2	"	1.45	0.27
BaCl_2	"	1.5	0.28
MgCl_2	0.08M	1.5	0.19
CaCl_2	"	1.65	0.21
BaCl_2	"	1.8	0.22
Quaternary ammonium salts :			
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$	0.16 M	5.2	1.8
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$	"	4.3	1.4
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$	0.08M	8.3	2.2
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$	"	7.6	2.0
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$	0.02 M	18.0	3.6
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$	"	22.5	5.0
CTA Br	0.012 M	73.5	21.6
CPCI	"	93.0	34.0
CTABr	0.006 M	81.0	16.5
CPCI	"	101.0	21.0

12. S. Lindienbaum and G. E. Boyd, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 911.13. S. K. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1957 **5**, 85-90.

FIG. 4

Fig. 4. Correlation of Selectivity Coefficient with hydrated ionic radius and Debye Hückel parameter a° .

An attempt has also been made to correlate the Selectivity Coefficients which gives a measure of the selectivities of ions for montmorillonite with some other properties of the ions, viz., hydrated ionic radius¹⁴ and the parameter a° ¹⁵ of the Debye-Hückel equation,— $\log \gamma_{\pm} = A\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + Ba^\circ\sqrt{\mu})$. It appears from the graphs in Fig. 4 that Rb^+ and Cs^+ are more strongly attached than what is required by hydrated ionic radii. NH_4^+ and K^+ which, as expected, stay close together and occupy an intermediate position between the two pairs Rb^+ , Cs^+ , and Na^+ , Li^+ . On the other hand, if $1/a^\circ$ is plotted against $\log K$, a straight line is obtained. The latter strongly suggests that in the process of desorption of cobalt hexammine ion from the clay surface by smaller inorganic cations the Debye-Hückel a° rather than the hydrated ionic radius show a better correlation. Similar findings have been reviewed by Kressman and Kitchener¹⁶ who have also reported their own results with phenol sulphonate resin exchangers, which agree with the above.

DEPT. OF CHEMISTRY,
NORTH BENGAL UNIVERSITY,
DIST, DARJEELING, WEST BENGAL.

&
DEPT. OF AGRICULTURE,
CALCUTTA UNIVERSITY.

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14. Landolt-Bornstein's Tabellen, Ergänzungsband, 1936, IIIC, 2059.

15. R. H. Stokes and R. A. Robinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1870.

16. T. R. E. Kressman and J. A. Kitchener, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190, and *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 118.